

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

Project number: 732506

D3.8

Second Data Pitch Consultations

**Coordinator: Johanna Walker, University of
Southampton**

**With contributions from: Elena Simperl, University of
Southampton, Anna Hammond, University of
Southampton**

Quality reviewer: Gonçalo Faria, Beta-i

Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)
Nature	Other
Document URL	
Work package	WP3 - Data and Data Providers' Liaison
Contractual delivery date:	31st March 2018
Actual delivery date:	29th March 2018
Version:	1
Keywords:	Consultation, Challenges, Data

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Abstract

This document outlines the work undertaken in the second round of Data Pitch to deliver the consultation on challenges for Data Pitch, including the public consultation, Advisory Board consultation, expert discussions and consultation with data providers.

Executive summary

Data Pitch is an innovation programme that aims to bring large organisations with data together with startups and small to medium enterprises with data skills to solve some of the problems that face society today.

To do this it must identify the highest impact economic and social problems that can be solved with data (“high impact challenges”). These challenges are defined in part by companies willing to share their data in order to solve problems of concern to them (“data providers”) but also in part through a process of consultation with industry experts, start ups and citizens.

In the first round of Data Pitch we identified a number of potential challenges which were refined with expert input and presented in the consultation for views on their importance. This resulted in challenges in the domains of Data Analytics, Retail, Transport, Sport, Data Management, Health and Wellness, Smart Manufacturing, Empowering Users Online, Living, Lifelong Learning and Tourism. The consultation also sought views on which data could be used to address these challenges.

This deliverable outlines how we are running the consultation process in Round 2 based on our learning and successes in Round 1.

The consultation will run for a month after which all input will be analysed at a workshop involving the Data Pitch team and invited experts. The final output of this consultation will be a number (yet to be determined) of clearly defined challenges. This will be included in the Call for Applications for Data Pitch Round 2. Startups/ SMEs will need to demonstrate that they have a clear plan to address these challenges in a financially sustainable way in order to be selected the Data Pitch Innovation Programme.

1. Introduction

A core part of the Data Pitch programme is to identify critical cross-sector and cross-border challenges from a wide array of Big Data Value stakeholders, including the data owners we partner with. These challenges will shape the innovation life cycle and determine the design of the innovation instruments used and the thematic scope of the incubator.

A challenge as defined by Data Pitch is a social or economic problem for which a solution (or solutions) can be developed with closed, shared or open data, or a combination of all three.

This document explains the challenges, describes the methods of collection of ideas for the challenges and presents some early ideas and plans for M13-M18, the period in which we are developing the second call.

1.1 Aims of this Deliverable

This deliverable describes Data Pitch's process for consultation for collection of input and ideas for our challenges.

This deliverable is related to Round 2 of the Data Pitch call and is the second deliverable on high-impact consultations.

This document is structured as follows: In section 1, we review the open innovation approach to solving high impact challenges adopted by Data Pitch. Section 2 discusses our process for identifying key challenges and section 3 outlines the specific steps of our consultative approach to defining the challenges and the output.

1.2 The Data Pitch Concept

Data Pitch brings together corporates and public sector organisations, that have data, with startups and SMEs which work with data. It is centred around an innovation competition with several tracks, which describe challenges set by data-owning organisations and through a method of crowdsourcing, and a 6-month incubation programme to help startups and SMEs develop solutions to meet these challenges.

The data sets can be open, shared or closed. The startups and SMEs will put forward proposals for creating high impact, innovative products and services in response to the challenges. The challenges will cover a number of topics including smart cities, food & agriculture, amongst others. Data Pitch manages the overall programme, organises the competition and selection process, funds the best ideas, and supports the best ideas through business incubation. The competition will be run twice, with multiple tracks and challenges in each call. Each call will draw upon challenges and data sets from several organisations. The startups and SMEs selected for the first call are currently incubating until 31st July 2018.

The second Data Pitch call opens at 12:00 noon Central European Summer Time (CEST) 2nd July 2018 and will remain open until 12:00 noon Central European Summer Time (CEST) 2nd October 2018. Selected ideas will receive up to €100,000 equity-free investment and will be entered into the 6-month acceleration programme.

1.3 The Challenge Concept

Through open innovation, Data Pitch supports the development of credible, sustainable data products or services. However, in order that these new products or services are directed at solving the most important and valuable problems, socially and economically, it is necessary to identify and formulate the most high-impact challenges that can be addressed with data. Challenges can be formulated in a number of ways, but there are key best practices that must be adhered to, which were described in Deliverable 3.4.

Data Pitch consortium partners, Beta-i and The Open Data Institute have in-depth experience of developing and running challenges. Data Pitch is led by their experience. The ODI defined their key best practices in the publication, 'What Works in Open Data Challenges.' These include:

- Setting clear objectives that reflect the primary interests of all core stakeholders. Our consultation described by this deliverable is a key part of this.
- Designing a bespoke challenge structure that reflects these primary objectives. Our twin tracks - exploratory and provider-driven - enable this.
- Committing to open design principles and being prepared to iterate or adjust plans. To achieve this we are in close collaboration with our data providers and encourage them, where appropriate, to test their data and challenge ideas in datathon settings, which are described below. Further, our reaching out to a wide variety of citizens and communities is very much in line with the principles of open.
- Optimising return on investment by running multiple challenges over an extended period. Our community of innovators, policy experts and entrepreneurs will leverage across challenges.

1.4 Data Pitch Challenges

Data Pitch challenges take three forms, in order to assure the inclusion of the most important challenges and access the widest range of shared data to solve the challenges.

- (1) 'Data Provider Challenges', where the challenge domain is defined in consultation with an organisation that wishes to provide data based on their insights and our knowledge of high impact areas;
- (2) 'Sectoral Challenges', where the domain is defined in consultation with citizens and experts via the process described in this deliverable;
- (3) 'Open Challenge', where the domain is undefined, is meant to offer a platform for groundbreaking, impactful ideas which did not fit elsewhere in the call. This is not a challenge for incremental ideas. Instead, it provides an opportunity for start-ups that are working on something truly transformative; that can be applied over a wide range of industries; and has the potential to totally reinvent a process or find a solution for a previously unsolvable problem.

Background material defining, explaining and supporting more extended concepts such as open innovation and data accelerators is available in the deliverable [D3.4 Data Pitch First Consultations, Section 2. Background](#)

1.5 Round 1

The consultations in Round 1 resulted in sectoral challenges in the following domains:

- Health and Wellness,
- Empowering Users Online (trust and personal safety),
- Lifelong Learning (education),
- Living (accommodation and living standards),
- Smart Manufacturing
- Tourism.

The details of each of these challenges can be found in Annex 1. These challenges were determined to meet the following criteria:

- Impact: Extremely high impact areas
- Accessibility and speed: Multiple datasets that are currently closed can be accessed in these tracks, which are not as subject to tight regulatory processes as other potential tracks
- Opportunity to leverage network effects: By focusing on tracks that are high priority for governments at local, regional, national and international levels, and that affect the continued functioning of society for all people, Data Pitch's work can engage with other efforts in these arenas to increase impact

These challenges produced the following results in terms of successful applicants to the accelerator:

Sectoral Challenge	Eligible Applications	Interviews	Accelerated Start ups
Health and Wellness	29	12	4
Lifelong Learning	4	1	0
Smart Manufacturing	16	8	4
Tourism	15	7	3
Living	4	1	0
Empowering Users Online	14	4	1
Data Provider Challenge	Applications	Interviews	Accelerated Start ups
Transport	6	3	1
Retail	8	4	1
Sports and Recreation	6	3	0
Data Management	7	4	2
Data Analytics	5	5	2

We also had 28 applications to our Open challenge. However, no application was deemed sufficiently innovative and groundbreaking for inclusion in the accelerator.

The learning in Call 1 has informed our approach to consultations in Call 2, particularly in terms of the domains we are selecting (2.1 - 2.4) and how we identify (name) the challenges (3.6).

2. The Pre-consultation Process – Call 2

This section outlines the process for selecting challenge domains for consultation.

2.1 Big Data Value Association Key Verticals

In October 2017 the Big Data Value Association published the Strategic Roadmap and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) version 4.0. This identified the following verticals as those in which industry surveys have shown or predicted significant gains from data innovation:

- a. Environmental and geospatial data
- b. Energy
- c. Mobility, transport and logistics
- d. Manufacturing and production
- e. Public sector
- f. Healthcare
- g. Media and content
- h. Finance
- i. Telecoms
- j. Retail
- k. Tourism

2.2 Round 1 Verticals

In Round 1 we have already approached some of these verticals as follows:

Vertical	Round 1 Activity
Environmental and geospatial data	Not covered
Energy	Not covered
Mobility, transport and logistics	Data Provider challenge; one startup accepted into accelerator
Manufacturing and production	Sectoral challenge: many applications, several companies accepted into accelerator
Public sector	Partially addressed through Living and Lifelong Learning sectoral challenges; no companies accepted into accelerator
Healthcare	Sectoral challenge: many applications, several companies accepted into accelerator
Media and content	Partially addressed through Empowering Users Online challenge; one company accepted into accelerator
Finance	Not covered
Telecoms	Not covered
Retail	Data Provider challenge; one startup accepted into accelerator
Tourism	Sectoral challenge: several companies accepted into accelerator

Further, our experience reviewing applications and interviewing startups for the accelerator in Call 1 has informed us that the Automotive, Pharmaceutical, Retail and Smart Manufacturing domains have a wealth of interesting and innovative startups utilising shared data operating within them.

2.3 Domains selected for Round 2

Our list of domains for Round 2 therefore includes:

- a. Environmental and geospatial data
- b. Energy
- c. Mobility, transport and logistics
- d. Manufacturing and production
- e. Public sector (Smart Cities)
- f. Pharmaceutical
- g. Media and content
- h. Finance
- i. Telecoms
- j. Retail
- k. Automotive

We are currently consulting with Data Providers in the Environmental and geospatial, Transport, Media and content and Retail sectors. However, these discussions are not expected to be completed until May 2018, and it is possible that more organisations may approach us before this is finalised. This means that we are having to be flexible as to which challenges are Sectoral Challenges and which Data Provider challenges. For instance, we are currently in negotiation to have a leading French bank provide a Finance challenge. However, because of the high impact and relevance of this sector, we are also preparing a Sectoral challenge alongside, to ensure that we are definitely able to provide a challenge in this domain, regardless of the outcome of the discussions. After a number of iterations, the pre-selection process has resulted in the following Sectoral challenges being presented for consultation with experts, start-ups and citizens:

2.4. Domains for Sectoral Challenge Consultation

- Automotive (design, development, manufacturing, marketing, and selling of motor vehicles)
- Pharmaceuticals (discovery, development, production, marketing of drugs for use as medications)
- Telecommunications (incl. wireless operators, satellite companies, cable companies, ISPs etc.)
- Smart cities (technologies, devices, infrastructure etc. that enhance the quality of urban services)
- Energy (production and sale of energy, incl. fuel extraction, manufacturing, refining distribution etc.)
- Finance and insurance (incl. consumer, wholesale banking, (re)insurance and pension funding etc.)

3.The Consultation

The challenges will be developed during an extensive process of consultation across sectors and stakeholders. In this way we will identify and develop high impact challenges that meet economic

and social needs. This process has already begun and will continue until the second Call for Applicants is launched.

Our consultation stakeholders fall approximately into three categories, for whom we have developed approaches as outlined in Section.

Stakeholders	Activity
Data Providers	During discussions for the provision of data sets to the Data Pitch programme, we will assist data providers in developing and defining key challenges within the appropriate tracks.
Industry Experts	We are seeking ideas from experts via our consultation, attending events and our Advisory Board.
Citizens and Communities	An important stakeholder in the creation of questions for challenges is the public, whether individuals, in scientific communities or innovation networks. This enables us to make sure we prioritise problems that matter to a variety of communities and demographics.

This section will outline our consultation on high impact challenges and, the process we will be following. The result will contribute to the Call.

3.1. Core Activity – High Impact Challenge Online Consultation

The aim of the consultation is to engage stakeholders and seek their views on three key issues. This will enable both crowdsourcing of ideas from interested parties such as start ups alongside input from industry and data experts. The key areas are:

1. What they believe the high impact challenges domains are
2. The most relevant challenge questions in each domain
3. What are the key technologies that could be used to address these challenges

Our Advisory Board will also be consulted using this format.

3.2. Consultation Strategy Round 2

Our consultation strategy follows the process below. This is broadly similar to the process in Round 1 but involves more detailed contribution from experts in defining the wording and background to the challenges prior to the workshop.

- Map Stakeholders - these have been described above. We have also sought to know more about these by including demographic questions in the consultation.
- Determine Methods and Tools – The process described in Section 2 was used to define a set of possible challenge domains. This was then developed and extended to create a full set of consultation questions.

- Create Consultation Webpage - This is done in line with the strategy and practices described in *Data Pitch Deliverable 6.1, Online presence and Marketing Tools*
- Announce and Communicate – The consultation was widely publicised using social media, traditional media and media partnerships including on the Data Pitch website.
- Run Consultation – The consultation was available from February 21 – March 21 2018
- Analyse Content – The results of the consultation will be analysed by an external advisor during the last week of March.
- Provide Synopsis of Consultation Results – The results will inform the Call published for Round 2 of Data Pitch in July 2018
- Devise challenges based on online consultation results, expert interviews, data provider interviews, advisory board and sectoral expertise of consortium members.

3.3. Compliance

Our consultation is compliant with the European Commission Minimum Standards:

- Clarity: Clear content of the consultation process. We have followed the European Commission format, and included supporting documentation.
- Targeting: In order to ensure that all relevant parties have an opportunity to express their opinions, we are targeting the following groups in the following manner (non-exhaustive list)
- Publication: The consultation will be located online at datapitch.eu, in line with single access point best practice.
- Time Limits: The consultation will be open for one month (21st February 2018 to 21st March 2018). Given the highly targeted approach to consultation this will be sufficient time.
- Feedback: The final output will be included in the Call for Applications published on July 2, 2018.

3.4. Consultation

The Consultation can be found at:

<https://datapitch.eu/news/want-to-play-your-part-in-helping-to-design-data-pitch/>

Associated Frequently Asked Questions can be found at: FAQs

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfCAVW6iv0N315rYIX-2zMukJ4xKKNby2EfeGK28n5DRIn7BQ/viewform>

3.5. Analysis

The consultation is continuously reviewed and any suggestions regarding the provision of data are followed up appropriately as soon as they are received.

After the consultation closes, an external expert, who assisted in developing the challenge definitions in Round 1, will analyse the input.

3.6. Workshop

In Round 1 the Workshop was a central part of selecting the challenges. However, in Round 2 we have done more pre-selection and prioritization work as well as analysing the results of the consultation beforehand. The aim of the Challenges Workshop in this round is to ensure there are no gaps in the background nor overlaps in the challenges. It will also ensure that we have named the challenges correctly like education and lifelong learning.

The workshop will be attended by the members of the Data Pitch consortium responsible for developing the Sectoral and Data Provider challenges and will be led by an experienced outside facilitator who also led the Workshop in Round 1.

3.7. Supporting Activities – Events and Data Provider Interviews

3.7.1. Expert Discussions

We spoke to a wide range of experts. Our experts are expert on the industry, which means they may work in, consult to, research or regulate the industry. We attended events that take the form of roundtables – specific topic discussions where all participants are given equal opportunity to participate – where attendees are people with a wide variety of technical, entrepreneurial, and data governance backgrounds, in order to capture further insights not included in the consultation. We also attended expert presentations.

3.7.2. Interviews - Data Providers

As part of our negotiations with data providers, including organisations and EU projects, we have been elucidating key challenges that they wish to address. These have largely taken place during teleconferences. The full list will be available when the call is published. During the negotiations that precede the acceleration, we will define with data experimenters and providers the quantitative metrics that will determine the success of the experiment (e.g. 20% faster execution time; +5% in confidence of estimation compared to state of the 50 users for the new app; sales adding up to 50K€, etc).

3.8. Call Output

The proceeds of the Consultation will be a minimum of 12 clear challenges, related to datasets, that will be published on the website and also in Deliverable 4.3 Summary of Round 2 (M30).

4. Call 1 Challenges

A full list of the Call 1 Challenges can be viewed and downloaded from the Data Pitch website (<https://datapitch.eu/challenges/>).